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Food preservatives knowledge training and terms of use

Faldi ^{1,*}, Hasyrul Hamzah ², Rahman Anshari ³, Chaerul Fadly Mochtar Lutfi M ², Bambang Setiaji ³, Suwoko ³, Alfin Syahrian Dwi Nugraha ² and Salsabila Azzahra ²

¹ Faculty of Engineering, Informatics Engineering Study Program, Universitas Muhammadiyah Kalimantan Timur, Samarinda, East Borneo, Indonesia.

² Faculty of Pharmacy, Universitas Muhammadiyah Kalimantan Timur, Samarinda, East Borneo, Indonesia.

³ Faculty of Business and Political Economics, Management Study Program, Universitas Muhammadiyah Kalimantan Timur, Samarinda, East Borneo, Indonesia.

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Abstract

With the development of technology both in the food and non-food industries. This service activity uses a survey data collection method that focuses on the level of public awareness about food preservatives and the conditions for their use through webinar activities. Data analysis was carried out by taking into account the number of respondents from each question so that the results were in the form of a description and also presented in the form of a pie chart. Based on the results of the service, it can be concluded that as many as 88.5% of respondents already know the types of preservatives. public knowledge about the requirements for the use of preservatives has a percentage of 86.4% for people who answered they already know, this figure is sufficient to say that the community already knows enough about the requirements for the use of preservatives, and 7.3% for those who answered maybe know

Keywords: Food Preservation; Knowledge, Food; Preservatives

1. Introduction

With the development of technology in both the food and non-food industries, more and more choices are available for consumers or the general public to obtain special food raw materials for large, medium and small scale industries as well as in-home manufacturing that suits their needs [1], [2] There is no denying that food is essential for life. Therefore food safety is important for consumers as well as for the food industry. The single most important thing that is done to improve the quality and taste of food is to use a preservation mechanism. Food preservatives are additives that are used consistently by mixing them with food with the aim of improving the nutrition and taste of the food concerned and stopping the decay process [2].

The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that 1 in 10 people fall ill each year from eating contaminated food and 420,000 die as a result [3] Indonesia is a country that has abundant natural and cultural wealth, especially in the culinary or food sector. Quoted from [4] food must contain nutrients to fulfill this function and be safe, and it seems that food and drinks cannot be separated from preservatives and coloring agents. European Parliament and Council Regulation No. 95/2/EC Concerning Food Additives Other than Colors and Sweeteners says "Food additive" means any substance which is not normally consumed as a food in itself and is not normally used as a food additive whether it has nutritional value or not, which is intentionally added to food for technological purposes intended for the manufacture, processing, preparation, treatment, packaging, transportation or storage of said food product, or as may reasonably be expected for the result, therein or product. by-products become directly or indirectly a component of the food.

* Corresponding author: Faldi

Based on the Regulation of the Head of the Drug and Food Control Agency of the Republic of Indonesia Number 36 of 2013 concerning Maximum Limits for Use of Preservative Food Additives. Preservatives are food additives to prevent or inhibit fermentation, acidification, decomposition and other damage to food caused by microorganisms (Regulation of the Head of the Food and Drug Supervisory Agency of the Republic of Indonesia Number 36 of 2013 concerning Maximum Limits for Use of Preservative Food Additives, 2013) [5]. Thus, the general public who are the final consumers of these foodstuffs should have basic knowledge in order to be able to identify food ingredients with dangerous preservatives, and at the same time, they can also carry out the preservation process. The purpose of this community service (PKM) is to advance the community through counseling, discusses existing issues in detail other matters mentioned here including community awareness, associated with trusted natural preservatives.

2. Material and methods

This service activity uses a survey data collection method that focuses on the level of public awareness of food preservatives and the conditions for their use through webinar activities. Data from interviewees provided to respondents anonymously (online) via Google Form is the type of data collected for this project where interviewees have provided questions and answers that have been received regarding the level of public knowledge about Information technology. Data analysis was carried out by taking into account the number of respondents to each question so that the results are in the form of a description and are also presented in the form of a pie chart [6].

3. Results and discussion

Figure 1 Knowledge of types of preservatives

Figure 2 Knowledge of Requirements for using preservatives

Then the results of the questionnaire on the public knowledge section regarding the requirements for using preservatives have a percentage of 86.4% for people who answer they already know, this figure is enough to say that people already know enough about the requirements for using preservatives, and 7.3% for those who answer may know.

The implementation of PKM activities took place on Saturday, September 25 2022, which was held by the Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Muhammadiyah East Kalimantan, with Zoom meeting media from 09.15 to 11.30 WITA with 191 participants. In general, people already know how important it is to know what preservatives are. Based on the questionnaire given by the committee to the community, it was found that 88.5% of the public knew about preservatives. As well as 7.9% for respondents who answered maybe.

Documentation supporting PKM activities that have been carried out is shown in the following figures.

Figure 3 Presentation from the Speaker about Copywriting

4. Conclusion

Based on the results of the dedication, it can be concluded that as much as 88.5% of respondents already know the types of preservatives. Community knowledge regarding the requirements for using preservatives has a percentage of 86.4% for people who answer they already know, this figure is enough to say that the community already knows enough about the requirements for using preservatives, and 7.3% for those who answer maybe know

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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